

Advancing Europe's Strategic Priorities for Clean Energy and Mobility Through V2G

From Passive Transport to Active Power Plants

CEI-Sphere

part of EU**CloudEdgeIoT**.eu

Unlocking the flexibility of millions of "Batteries on Wheels" to power the European grid

Europe's energy system is entering a new phase of complexity. With the rapid electrification of transport, electric vehicles (EVs) are becoming one of the largest distributed energy resources.

This report explores how Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) infrastructure is transforming Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) from a pilot concept into a scalable commercial reality. By mapping data flows, infrastructure, and regulatory aspects, it highlights how collaboration between automotive manufacturers, energy providers, and end-users can unlock significant system value.

Unlocking the Flexibility of Vehicle Batteries for Everyone

As renewable energy generation grows, maintaining grid balance is critical. V2G technology allows mobile EV batteries to actively support the electricity grid, charging when renewables are abundant and discharging during peak demand

114 TWh

The flexible capacity European EV batteries could provide by 2030 (enough to power ~30 million homes)

Potential annual system cost savings by 2040 through smart charging and V2G.

€20 B

**>90%
Reduction**

How much V2G could reduce the need for costly stationary grid storage.

The projected number of EVs on European roads by 2035, serving as an immense, distributed energy reserve.

**80-90+
Million EVs**

The Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) Continuum V2G requires a highly dynamic, real-time data ecosystem to coordinate millions of assets. The CEI Continuum provides the technical foundation:

IoT Layer

Physical assets like EVs, bidirectional chargers, and smart meters generating real-time telemetry (State of Charge, user schedules).

Edge Layer

Local controllers and gateways enabling low-latency, on-site decision-making and optimal power flow.

Cloud Layer

Centralised platforms for virtual power plant (VPP) orchestration, energy market trading, and AI-driven forecasting.

From Concept to Market Reality

Commercial Successes

New partnerships between aggregators and automotive OEMs are enabling innovative “zero-cost charging” models, where V2G revenues offset electricity costs.

- **Renault & The Mobility House (FR/DE):** AC V2G service offering free driving credits through smart charging
- **Octopus Energy (UK/EU):** “Power Pack” tariff with up to 210 kWh/month of free charging via the Kraken platform

European Large-Scale Pilots (LSPs)

Scaling next-generation infrastructure

EU flagship pilots are validating Cloud-Edge-IoT solutions for smart energy and mobility.

- **Austria (O-CEI Pilot 3):** AI-driven optimisation of 5,000 electric delivery vehicles, reducing costs and supporting grid stability
- **Italy (O-CEI Pilot 7):** 5G-enabled smart charging in Milan for secure, real-time V2G interactions
- **Greece (COP-PILOT):** Digital twins and edge analytics for predictive maintenance and grid flexibility

Building the Open Ecosystem

Closing the *Regulatory and Standards Gap* while technical feasibility is proven, scaling V2G requires overcoming legal and standardisation hurdles. Europe must build a level playing field.

Harmonised Standards

Seamless "plug and charge" bidirectionality requires unified communication, notably ISO 15118-20, OCPP, and EEBUS.

Regulatory Enablers

Initiatives like the Electricity Market Design (EMD) reform and RED III are crucial for removing the "double taxation" of electricity and ensuring non-discriminatory access to vehicle data

Collaborating for Scale Major European task forces are aligning industry players to establish common rules:

Task 53

Driving multiparty interoperability testing for bidirectional charging worldwide

Coalition of the Willing (CoW)

An ambitious cross-industry alliance creating blueprints to make V2G a scalable market reality.

Sustainable Transport Forum (STF) & D4E

Shaping the digital backbone and governance models for data-driven energy systems

This document provides insights into how CEI infrastructures developed in European Flagship projects can contribute to the systemic transformation of Europe's energy and mobility sectors. This report is a public deliverable (D3.1) of the CEI-Sphere project, authored by VDI, with peer review and contributions from consortium partners and domain experts